

the reaction was over, the stopper was rinsed with 5 ml distilled water and 10 ml of 1*N* sulphuric acid was added. The contents were shaken for a minute and the unreacted Ce(IV) was titrated against ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as indicator. A blank was also run under identical conditions and the recovery of the sample was calculated with the difference in the titre values of the blank and the actual experiment.

as the final reaction products. On the basis of stoichiometry and the identification of final oxidation products we conclude the same reaction path as reported earlier⁶.

TABLE—DETERMINATION OF SOME SUGARS WITH THE PROPOSED METHOD

Sample	Sample taken (mg)	Actual Equivalents of Ce(IV) consumed/mole of the sample	Sugars found (mg) by calculation	Error %
1. Xylose	2.5000	10	2.5200	+0.80
	5.0000	10	5.0500	+1.00
	7.5000	10	7.5700	+0.93
2. Glucose	2.5000	12	2.5200	+0.80
	5.0000	12	5.0600	+1.20
	7.5000	12	7.5800	+1.06
3. Galactose	2.5000	12	2.5300	+1.20
	5.0000	12	5.0500	+1.00
	7.5000	12	7.5600	+0.80
4. Fructose	3.5000	14	3.5350	+1.00
	7.0000	14	7.0600	+0.85
	10.5000	14	10.6000	+0.94
5. Sorbose	3.5000	14	3.5420	+1.20
	7.0000	14	7.0600	+0.85
	10.5000	14	10.6000	+0.95
6. Maltose	2.2000	26	2.1800	-0.90
	4.4000	26	4.3500	-1.13
	8.8000	26	8.8900	+1.02
7. Lactose	2.5000	26	2.4800	-0.80
	5.0000	26	4.9500	-1.00
	7.5000	26	7.4200	-1.06
8. Sucrose	2.5000	26	2.4800	-0.80
	5.0000	26	4.9400	-1.20
	7.5000	26	7.4300	-0.93

Discussion

The effect of the concentration of nitric acid, temperature, the amount of Ce(IV) reagent and the reaction time was studied. Boiling of the reaction mixture even for 40-60 minutes does not bring any change in the speed of the reaction and the recovery of the sample. Inconvenience is noticed in observing the end point.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was also established and the final oxidation products were identified. It was found that the aldoses give formic acid as the final oxidation product, while ketoses evolve carbon dioxide in addition to formic acid. Disaccharides also give formic acid and carbon dioxide

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Spectrophotometric Studies of Complexing Equilibria Involved Between Hafnium and Bromopyrogallol Red and Nitroso R Salt in Aqueous Solution

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THE quantitative equilibria involved between Hf(IV) and *o*-(2, 7-dibromo-4, 5, 6-trihydroxy-3-oxo-3H-xanthen-9-yl) benzene sulphonic acid (Bromopyrogallol Red, i. e. BPGR) and 3-hydroxy-4-nitroso 2,7-naphthalene disulphonic acid (Nitroso R salt, i.e. NRS) in aqueous solution is being reported in this paper. With NRS, however, some potentiometric work⁴ on the nature and stability constants of hafnium complexes have been reported⁵ earlier.

Experimental

Apparatus : Beckman DU-2 Spectrophotometer with glass cells of 1 cm. path length was used. An Elico pH meter model LI-10 was used for pH measurements.

Reagents : Solution of hafnium oxychloride (spec-pure) was prepared by dissolving the sample in a known quantity of HClO₄ in such a way that after dilution the stock solution was 1 × 10⁻³ M in 2M HClO₄ acid. Pure and crystallized samples of BPGR and NRS were used for preparing the stock solutions of the ligands.

Results and Discussion

Acid Dissociation Constants : The pK values of the ligands were determined by the method of Albert and Serjeant¹ at room temperature (30°). The pK₂, pK₃ and pK₄ values for BPGR are 5.21, 9.15 and 11.48 whereas pK₃ value for NRS is 7.10. The pK values relating to the dissociation of sulphonic acid groups

(pK_1 in BPGR and pK_1 and pK_2 in NRS) in these ligands could not be obtained under the present conditions of study.

Absorption spectra and composition of the chelate : Three series of solutions in different ratios of metal : ligand (1:1, 1:4 and 4:1) were prepared and the acid concentration of these solutions was adjusted from pH 1.0 to pH 2.0 in all the cases. The absorption spectra was then recorded in the entire visible range. pH values above 2.0 could not be adjusted due to the hydrolysis of hafnium.

In the present case, Hf forms only one 2:1 (M:L) chelate with BPGR in the pH range of 1.2 to 1.8 having λ_{max} 520nm. However, the detailed study of this chelate was done at pH 1.8 and at 530 nm at which the difference in absorbance between the chelate and the ligand is maximum.

Similarly in case of NRS, at pH 1.5, λ_{max} shifts from 370 nm to 390 nm and remains the same upto pH 2.0. Above pH 2.0 a further shift in λ_{max} (400 nm) occurs. In the present work the first chelate was studied at pH 1.5 and at 430 nm. The other chelate expected to form above pH has been found to be unstable and hence could not be studied in detail.

Study of equilibrium : BPGR Chelate : The formation of 2:1 Hf: BPGR) chelate of hafnium with BPGR at pH 1.8 is complete within 10 mins. At this pH, the involvement of hydrolyzed species of hafnium, $[Hf(OH)]^{3+}$ may be considered for chelate formation.

The reaction thus, becomes,

The equilibrium constant, K, of the above reaction and the conditional stability constant, β , of the complex are related as follows :

$$\log \beta = -4 \log [H]^+ + \log K$$

Thus a plot of $\log \beta$ vs. $\log [H]^+$ should give a slope equal to -4.0 which is the number of protons liberated according to reaction (i). The intercept is equal to $\log K$, the equilibrium constant.

The values of β can be calculated at different acid concentrations (Table 1) by the methods reported earlier^{2,5}.

The values of $\log \beta$ are evaluated in this way and plotted against $\log [H]^+$, which gives a straight line. The value of the slope is equal to -3.8 (about 4) which is the number of protons liberated during reaction (i). The intercept is equal to 16.1 which is the $\log K$, the equilibrium constant of the reaction. Reaction (i) appears, therefore, to be correct with the $[Hf(OH)]^{3+}$ species participating in the complexation reaction.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF CONDITIONAL STABILITY CONSTANT OF BPGR CHELATE AT 530 nm*

pH	Absorbance of stoichiometric mixture	$Q \times 10^5$	$\beta \times 10^{-9}$	$\log [H]^+$	$\log \beta$
1.2	0.600	4.691	397.300	-1.2	11.5992
1.3	0.590	4.536	113.500	-1.3	11.0551
1.4	0.580	4.382	61.790	-1.4	10.7908
1.5	0.570	4.229	23.050	-1.5	10.3628
1.6	0.560	4.074	12.820	-1.6	10.1081
1.7	0.550	3.765	4.996	-1.7	9.6986
1.8	0.540	3.456	2.348	-1.8	9.3707

* Final conc. of $Hf^{4+}(A_T) = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ and of BPGR (B_T) = $0.50 \times 10^{-4} M$. Molar extinction coefficient of the chelate (E_C) and the ligand (E_L) at pH 1.8 = 12.40×10^3 and 5.92×10^3 respectively.

Hf-NRS Chelate : The 1:1 chelate formed with NRS is a fast reaction at pH 1.5. Its kinetic and the proton liberation studies could not be done. It was not possible to assume the reacting species of hafnium. Although the chelate has been found to be anionic in nature, its structure could not be suggested on the basis of present studies.

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2-Hydroxy-4-Methylpropiophenone Oxime (HMPOX) as an Analytical Reagent—Studies on Vanadium Chelate

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SEVERAL organic reagents¹⁻⁶ have been proposed for the gravimetric determination of vanadium(V) but very few afford precipitate which can be weighed as such. The present work was undertaken with the